

Appendix A: Examining the robustness of the spectral line fits

Due to the low signal-to-noise ratio present in the detected 700 MHz lines, as discussed in Sect. 4.1, it becomes imperative to evaluate the robustness of the Gaussian fits, particularly because the fitted parameters constitute key input parameters for the non-LTE analysis that follows. Figures A.1 to A.3 display corner plots (Foreman-Mackey, 2016) illustrating the probability density distribution functions for all the fitted components across the whole parameter range, for each of the CH lines. These figures display the probability density distributions of each free parameter alongside the projected 2D histogram for a given pair of parameters. The solid lines mark the best-fit of the distribution while the dashed lines mark the bounds of the 2σ confidence interval.

Fig. A.1. Clockwise from the top to bottom: Corner plots presenting the 2D histograms and probability distribution functions of the Gaussian line fitting parameters (Peak T_b , ν_{LSR} and $\Delta\nu$) for the 3.264 GHz (dark blue), 3.335 GHz (red), and 3.349 GHz (dark orange) spectra, respectively, for the cloud component at 51 km s⁻¹ (left), 57 km s⁻¹ (centre) and 60 km s⁻¹ (right). The solid coloured and dashed black lines indicate the best fit parameter values and the 2σ confidence intervals, respectively.

References

Foreman-Mackey, D. 2016, The Journal of Open Source Software, 1, 24. doi:10.21105/joss.00024

Fig. A.2. Same as Fig. A.1 but for the 701 MHz (top) and 724 MHz (bottom) spectra in cyan and green, respectively.

Fig. A.3. Same as Fig. A.1 but for the fit components toward the 65 km s⁻¹ (left) and 67 km s⁻¹ (right) clouds.

Appendix B: Non-detections of the CH 700 MHz lines

This Appendix presents the non-detections (down to the rms noise levels quoted in Table 2) of the rotationally excited lines of CH near 700 MHz towards Sgr B2 (M), M8, M17, W43, and DR21 Main, respectively. Figures B.1 to B.5 present the average continuum map at 700 MHz towards each source alongside their corresponding CH spectra extracted from a region enclosed in a $40''.4$ beam. This beam is centred at the position where the sub-mm/FIR continuum emission is the strongest and for which there exists previous observations of the sub-mm and FIR lines of CH.

Fig. B.1. Left: Colour map displaying the background continuum emission at 700 MHz towards Sgr B2 (M) alongside white contours marking continuum emission levels from $1.8\times$, $2\times$, $4\times$, $7\times$ and $10\times 1\sigma$ where $1\sigma = 2.7\times 10^{-2}$ Jy/beam. The filled white ellipses on the bottom left-hand corner displays the synthesised beam and the blue circle marks the position towards which the spectra of the first rotationally excited lines of CH are extracted from. Right: From top-to-bottom the resulting baseline subtracted spectra of the 701 MHz, 703 MHz, 722 MHz and 724 MHz lines of CH.

Fig. B.2. Same as Fig. B.1 but towards M8, where the contours are plotted for continuum emission levels from $1\times$, $2\times$, $4\times$, $7\times$ and $10\times 1\sigma$ where $1\sigma = 0.24$ Jy/beam.

Fig. B.3. Same as Fig. B.1 but towards M17, where the contours are plotted for continuum emission levels from $2\times$, $3\times$, $4\times$, $7\times$ and $10\times 1\sigma$ where $1\sigma = 0.25$ Jy/beam.

Fig. B.4. Same as Fig. B.1 but towards W43, where the contours are plotted for continuum emission levels from $1.08\times$, $1.12\times$, $2\times$, $3\times$, $4\times$, $7\times$ and $10\times 1\sigma$ where $1\sigma = 0.17$ Jy/beam.

Fig. B.5. Same as Fig. B.1 but towards DR21 Main, where the contours are plotted for continuum emission levels from $0.5\times$, $2\times$, $4\times$, $7\times$ and $10\times 1\sigma$ where $1\sigma = 1.3 \times 10^{-2}$ Jy/beam.